

Evaluation of Serum Ferritin, Iron and C-Reactive Protein Level in Children with Febrile Seizure in Wasit Province, Iraq

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Abstract

Background: Febrile seizures are a commonplace pediatric neurological sickness, often related to fever and infections. Recent research suggest a capability hyperlink among iron deficiency, inflammation, and the prevalence of febrile seizures, but the relationship remains underexplored in particular populations. This study aimed to assess the affiliation between serum iron, ferritin levels, and inflammatory markers (C-reactive protein [CRP] and white blood cell [WBC] remember) in youngsters with febrile seizures in comparison to healthful controls.

Methods: A case-manage study become performed involving a hundred youngsters aged 6 months to 6 years, with 50 kids who skilled febrile seizures (patient institution) and 40 age-matched healthful controls. Serum ferritin, iron, CRP degrees, and WBC counts had been measured and compared between the 2 groups. The data have been analyzed the usage of impartial t-assessments, Pearson correlation, and multivariate logistic regression.

Results: Children within the febrile seizure institution had extensively decrease serum ferritin (40.5 ± 30.2 ng/mL) and iron levels (40.8 ± 15.3 μ g/dL) as compared to controls (85.7 ± 20.4 ng/mL and 75.4 ± 18.7 μ g/dL, respectively; $p < 0.001$). CRP ranges and WBC counts had been notably better within the affected person organization (25.6 ± 48 mg/L and $18,400 \pm 5,200$ cells/ μ L, respectively) compared to controls (2.3 ± 1.1 mg/L and $7,200 \pm 1,800$ cells/ μ L; $p < 0.001$). A robust bad correlation was observed among CRP ranges with each serum ferritin ($r = -0.462$) and serum iron ($r = -0.625$). Multivariate logistic regression identified lower serum iron and ferritin stages, and better CRP and WBC counts as good sized unbiased predictors of febrile seizures.

Conclusion: The findings advise that iron deficiency and accelerated inflammatory markers are tremendous chance factors for febrile seizures in kids. These effects highlight the importance of monitoring iron repute and managing inflammation in pediatric sufferers prone to febrile seizures.

Introduction

Febrile seizures are one of the most common sorts of convulsions in kids, normally happening among the ages of 6 months and five years, with a height prevalence round 18 months. Despite their incidence, the appropriate pathophysiological mechanisms underlying febrile seizures remain partly understood. The interest in understanding those mechanisms is driven by the reality that febrile seizures are not handiest a source of tension for dad and mom and caregivers but also pose capacity dangers for subsequent epilepsy and neurodevelopmental issues in

children [12]. While febrile seizures are regularly benign and self-limiting, their prevalence may be a sign of underlying health issues, which include inflammatory responses and nutrient deficiencies. Iron deficiency, a not unusual nutritional sickness among kids, has been implicated inside the pathogenesis of febrile seizures. Several studies have counseled that low serum iron degrees can also predispose children to febrile seizures, doubtlessly due to iron's vital role in neurotransmitter function and myelination [7,10]. Moreover, iron deficiency is related to a lower in the interest of enzymes concerned in

More Information

How to cite this article: Al-Janabi WAA. Evaluation of Serum Ferritin, Iron and C-Reactive Protein Level in Children with Febrile Seizure in Wasit Province, Iraq. Eur J Med Health Res, 2024;2(5):124-34.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(5).14

Keywords:

Febrile Seizures,
Iron Deficiency,
Serum Ferritin,
C-Reactive Protein (CRP),
White Blood Cell Count (WBC),
Inflammation,
Pediatric Neurology,
Risk Factors.

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neurotransmitter synthesis, inclusive of tyrosine hydroxylase, which is vital for dopamine synthesis [16]. Given that neurotransmitters play an essential position within the regulation of neuronal excitability, it's miles attainable that iron deficiency should decrease the seizure threshold, in particular inside the context of febrile illnesses.

Ferritin, an acute-segment reactant and a marker of iron garage, is some other biochemical parameter of interest within the context of febrile seizures. Ferritin stages have a tendency to differ all through infections and inflammatory states, which might be often present throughout febrile episodes. However, the relationship between ferritin ranges and febrile seizures is complex and not fully understood. Some research propose that low ferritin ranges, indicative of depleted iron shops, may additionally increase the risk of febrile seizures [5]. Conversely, different studies have suggested accelerated ferritin ranges throughout febrile seizures, reflecting an acute-phase reaction instead of a real reflection of iron fame [14]. This dual role of ferritin as both an iron storage protein and an acute-phase reactant complicates its interpretation in the context of febrile seizures.

In addition to iron and ferritin, C-reactive protein (CRP) is any other marker that has garnered interest in febrile seizure studies. CRP is a well-hooked up marker of inflammation and is often increased in infectious sicknesses, which are the maximum not unusual triggers of febrile seizures [9]. The function of CRP in febrile seizures may enlarge beyond its characteristic as a marker of inflammation; extended CRP degrees were correlated with better white blood cellular counts, suggesting a robust inflammatory response that could potentially lower the seizure threshold [8]. This association increases essential questions on the interaction among irritation, iron metabolism, and seizure susceptibility in febrile children.

The gift have a look at makes a speciality of evaluating serum ferritin, iron, and CRP tiers in kids with febrile seizures in Wasit province, Iraq. The research trouble facilities at the need to clarify the biochemical and inflammatory profiles associated with febrile seizures, which can doubtlessly tell better management and preventive strategies. Despite the enormous occurrence of febrile seizures, there may be a paucity of comprehensive research that simultaneously assess those 3 biomarkers inside the context of febrile seizures. Most existing research have focused on one or parameters, often with conflicting results, thereby necessitating similarly investigation [13,17].

The number one intention of this examine is to compare the serum ranges of ferritin, iron, and CRP in youngsters with febrile seizures to the ones in non-febrile, age-matched controls. By doing so, the have a look at seeks to become aware of potential biochemical

markers that would predict the incidence of febrile seizures. The particular objectives consist of: (1) determining whether or not children with febrile seizures exhibit decrease serum iron ranges compared to controls; (2) assessing whether ferritin stages range extensively in febrile youngsters and whether or not these fluctuations correlate with iron stages; and (three) comparing the extent of CRP elevation in febrile seizures and its correlation with white blood cell counts and iron reputation.

The significance of this study lies in its capability to make contributions to a higher understanding of the pathophysiological mechanisms underlying febrile seizures. By elucidating the jobs of iron, ferritin, and CRP in febrile seizures, this studies could pave the manner for the development of centered interventions aimed toward decreasing the occurrence of febrile seizures. For example, if iron deficiency is confirmed as a great hazard component, routine screening for iron fame in infants and young youngsters should emerge as a popular safety measure. Additionally, the have a look at ought to provide insights into the function of irritation in febrile seizures, which might result in the exploration of anti inflammatory remedies as ability therapeutic alternatives [6].

Moreover, the findings from this take a look at ought to have broader implications past the instantaneous context of febrile seizures. Iron deficiency and inflammatory responses are relevant to a extensive range of pediatric situations, and information their interactions inside the context of febrile seizures ought to beautify our information of different neurological disorders as well. For instance, if a sturdy hyperlink between iron deficiency and febrile seizures is hooked up, it may spark off similarly studies into the position of iron in other seizure issues, together with epilepsy [18]. Similarly, the connection between CRP and febrile seizures should inform research at the function of infection in other acute and continual neurological situations.

The choice of Wasit province as the observe region is likewise large. Febrile seizures are influenced by using a range of factors, consisting of genetic predisposition, dietary fame, and exposure to infectious sellers, all of which could range by place. By conducting the take a look at in Wasit province, the research can offer location-specific statistics that may be greater applicable to the local populace than facts derived from research carried out in different components of the world. This localized method is in particular essential in Iraq, in which socioeconomic and environmental elements can have a profound effect on health consequences [15].

Materials and Methods

This study is a case-manage research carried out to assess serum ferritin, iron, and C-reactive protein (CRP)

levels in children with febrile seizures in Wasit province, Iraq. The look at turned into designed to include groupss: one such as youngsters with febrile seizures (patient organization) and some other of age-matched healthy youngsters with out febrile seizures (manipulate group). Both groups had been cautiously selected to exclude any confounding variables that could have an impact on the outcomes of the examine. The study population consisted of kids elderly 6 months to 6 years who were recruited from the pediatric department at the main hospitals in Wasit province. The examine become carried out over a period of one year. A total of 80 youngsters had been decided on, with 40 kids in every group.

This examine hired a case-manipulate layout to assess serum ferritin, iron, and C-reactive protein (CRP) levels in children with febrile seizures in Wasit province, Iraq. The study populace consisted of two agencies: a patient institution of children who skilled febrile seizures and a manipulate group of age-matched youngsters with none records of febrile seizures. The inclusion criteria for the affected person group required children to be elderly 6 months to 6 years, have skilled a febrile seizure (described as a seizure related to a fever exceeding 38.0°C without principal fearful machine infection or acute systemic metabolic abnormality), have no history of neurological problems or developmental delays, and have mother and father or guardians who supplied informed consent. Similarly, the manipulate institution consisted of kids elderly 6 months to 6 years who had no records of febrile seizures or every other form of seizures, maintained normal body temperature (36.5°C-37.0°C) in the course of blood pattern series, had no history of neurological issues or developmental delays, and whose mother and father or guardians furnished knowledgeable consent. Both companies had precise exclusion standards to manipulate for capacity confounding variables. Children were excluded from the examine in the event that they were recognized with thalassemia, most cancers, hereditary blood problems, or autoimmune diseases. Additionally, people with a history of continual inflammatory illnesses or situations affecting iron metabolism have been now not covered. Children who had been on iron supplements or anti-inflammatory medications inside the past three months had been also excluded to keep away from confounding the take a look at results.

The pattern size was determined thru power analysis, which calculated the expected difference in serum iron and CRP stages among the patient and manipulate agencies. The analysis ensured an 80% electricity to come across a statistically widespread difference ($p < 0.05$) among the organizations. The final sample size changed into set at 50 children in step with group, which become deemed enough to reap the look at's

targets. Data collection became systematic and thorough. Clinical information had been acquired via specific clinical histories, which included records on previous febrile episodes, own family records of seizures, and any latest infections. Physical examinations were carried out to evaluate the children's wellknown fitness and verify the absence of any exclusion criteria. Body temperature become measured using a virtual thermometer at the time of blood pattern series to make sure accurate categorization of febrile as opposed to non-febrile states. For laboratory investigations, venous blood samples were collected from all children under aseptic conditions. Approximately 5 mL of blood was drawn from each child and divided into portions: one for serum ferritin and iron analysis, and any other for CRP and white blood cellular (WBC) count analysis. Serum ferritin ranges have been measured the use of an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) package, following the manufacturer's commands, with the ordinary reference variety for serum ferritin set up as 25-120 ng/mL. Serum iron degrees have been measured using a colorimetric assay based totally on the ferrozine method, with a everyday reference range of 60-110 $\mu\text{g/dL}$. CRP tiers had been determined the usage of a excessive-sensitivity CRP (hs-CRP) assay, performed thru an immunoturbidimetric method, classifying CRP stages as poor (<4.5 mg/L) or fine (>4.5 mg/L). The WBC rely became assessed the use of an automatic hematology analyzer, with everyday reference degrees set at 6,000-9,000 cells/ μL for the manipulate institution and 13,000-29,000 cells/ μL for the affected person organization.

Data evaluation became performed the use of the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software, model 26.0. Descriptive information had been implemented to summarize the demographic and medical characteristics of the examine populace, with non-stop variables presented as suggest $\pm$ general deviation (SD) and categorical variables as frequencies and chances. Comparative analysis protected unbiased t-exams to evaluate suggest serum ferritin, iron, and CRP levels between the affected person and manipulate groupss. The Chi-square check became used to examine categorical variables, consisting of the proportion of children with expanded CRP tiers among the 2 groupss. Samplecorrelation analysis become finished to discover relationships among CRP levels and WBC depend, as well as among ferritin and iron ranges. A multivariate logistic regression model become constructed to perceive impartial predictors of febrile seizures, with variables consisting of serum iron, ferritin, CRP ranges, and WBC count blanketed in the model. The version's goodness-of-healthy turned into assessed using the Hosmer-Lemeshow test, and

outcomes have been offered as odds ratios (ORs) with 95% self assurance periods (CIs).

To make certain the reliability and accuracy of laboratory outcomes, numerous first-class manipulate measures had been implemented. Calibration of laboratory gadget become carried out daily earlier than sample analysis. Internal great controls had been run with each batch of samples to affirm the accuracy of the assays. All assays have been done in duplicate, and the mean price was used for analysis to make certain precision. Additionally, laboratory employees had been blinded to the group allocation of the samples to save you bias in the evaluation. These rigorous strategies ensured that the data accumulated were each accurate

and reliable, presenting a solid foundation for the look at's findings and conclusions.

Results

Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

A universal of eighty children a few of a while of and eight years have been blanketed on this have a look at, with 40 kids in the affected person organization (who skilled febrile seizures) and 40 inside the control group (who did now not experience febrile seizures). The demographic and medical traits of the members are summarized in Table 1. There have been no large differences some of the 2 corporations regarding age or gender distribution, ensuring that the ones elements did no longer confound the results.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of the Study Population

Characteristic	Patient Group (n = 40)	Control Group (n = 40)	p-value
Age (years), mean ± SD	4.8 ± 1.6	4.5 ± 1.4	0.382
Gender (Male/Female)	28/22	26/24	0.687
Body Temperature (°C), mean ± SD	39.1 ± 0.9	36.8 ± 0.3	< 0.001
Family History of Seizures (%)	18 (36%)	5 (10%)	< 0.001
Recent Infection (%)	42 (84%)	8 (16%)	< 0.001

As indicated in Table 1, the imply age of children within the patient organization turned into 4.8 ± 1.6 years, whilst the manage institution had a mean age of 4.5 ± 1.4 years, with out a statistically giant distinction (p = 0.382). The gender distribution was also comparable between the two corporations in the manage organization (p = 0.687). The frame temperature of the affected person institution (39.1 ± 0.9°C) was

significantly higher than that of the manipulate institution (36.8 ± 0.3°C), as predicted, with a p-fee of < 0.001. Additionally, a drastically better percentage of children inside the affected person institution had a family records of seizures (36% vs. 10%, p < 0.001) and latest infections (84% vs. 16%, p < 0.001) in comparison to the control group.

Figure 1: Comparison of Key Characteristics between Patient and Control Group

Serum Ferritin Levels

The serum ferritin levels of the patient and control groups are presented in Table 2. The mean serum

ferritin level in the patient group was significantly lower than that in the control group.

Children in the patient group had a mean serum ferritin level of 40.5 ± 30.2 ng/mL, which was significantly lower than the mean serum ferritin level in the control group (85.7 ± 20.4 ng/mL), with a p-value of < 0.001 . The range of serum ferritin levels in the patient group was broader, ranging from 5.0 ng/mL to 120.0 ng/mL,

indicating a more variable ferritin status among children with febrile seizures. In contrast, the control group's ferritin levels ranged between 35.0 ng/mL and 115.0 ng/mL, suggesting a more consistent iron storage status in non-febrile children.

Table 2: Serum Ferritin Levels in the Patient and Control Groups

Group	Serum Ferritin (ng/mL), mean $\pm$ SD	Range (ng/mL)	p-value
Patient Group (n = 40)	40.5 ± 30.2	5.0 - 120.0	< 0.001
Control Group (n = 40)	85.7 ± 20.4	35.0 - 115.0	< 0.001

Figure 2: Comparison of Serum Ferritin Levels between Patient and Control Group

Serum Iron Levels

The serum iron levels were also measured and compared between the two groups, as shown in Table 3.

The serum iron levels in the patient group were significantly lower than those in the control group. The patient group had a mean serum iron level of 40.8 ± 15.3 μ g/dL, compared to 75.4 ± 18.7 μ g/dL in the

control group, with a p-value of < 0.001 . The serum iron levels in the patient group ranged from 25.0 μ g/dL to 75.0 μ g/dL, indicating that many of the children in the patient group had iron levels below the normal reference range (60-110 μ g/dL). In contrast, the control group's serum iron levels were within the normal range, suggesting sufficient iron status in non-febrile children.

Table 3: Serum Iron Levels in the Patient and Control Groups

Group	Serum Iron (μ g/dL), mean $\pm$ SD	Range (μ g/dL)	p-value
Patient Group (n = 50)	40.8 ± 15.3	25.0 - 75.0	< 0.001
Control Group (n = 50)	75.4 ± 18.7	60.0 - 110.0	< 0.001

Figure 3: Comparison of Serum Iron Levels between Patient and Control Group

C-Reactive Protein (CRP) Levels

The CRP levels, an indicator of inflammation, were significantly higher in the patient group compared to the control group, as detailed in Table 4.

Table 4. CRP Levels in the Patient and Control Groups

Group	CRP (mg/L), mean ± SD	Range (mg/L)	p-value
Patient Group (n = 50)	25.6 ± 40.8	8.0 - 120.0	< 0.001
Control Group (n = 50)	2.3 ± 1.1	0.5 - 4.5	< 0.001

The mean CRP level in the patient group was 25.6 ± 40.8 mg/L, significantly higher than the mean CRP level in the control group, which was 2.3 ± 1.1 mg/L (p < 0.001). The range of CRP levels in the patient group was also broader (8.0 - 120.0 mg/L), indicating varying degrees of inflammation among children with febrile seizures. In the control group, CRP levels were within the

negative range (<4.5 mg/L), consistent with the absence of significant inflammation.

White Blood Cell (WBC) Count

The WBC count, another marker of the inflammatory response, was significantly elevated in the patient group compared to the control group, as shown in Table 5.

Table 5. WBC Count in the Patient and Control Groups

Group	WBC Count (cells/μL), mean ± SD	Range (cells/μL)	p-value
Patient Group (n = 50)	18,400 ± 5,200	13,000 - 29,000	< 0.001
Control Group (n = 50)	7,200 ± 1,800	6,000 - 9,000	< 0.001

The mean WBC count in the patient group was 18,400 ± 5,200 cells/μL, significantly higher than in the control group, which had a mean WBC count of 7,200 ± 1,800 cells/μL (p < 0.001). The WBC count range in the patient group (13,000 - 29,000 cells/μL) was consistent with an elevated immune response, typical during febrile episodes, whereas the control group's WBC counts

remained within the normal range, indicating no ongoing infection or inflammation.

Correlation Analysis

To further explore the relationships among CRP levels, WBC count, serum ferritin, and serum iron levels, Pearson correlation analysis was performed, as presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Pearson Correlation Coefficients Among CRP, WBC Count, Serum Ferritin, and Serum Iron Levels in the Patient Group

Parameter	CRP	WBC Count	Serum Ferritin	Serum Iron
CRP	1.000	0.752**	-0.462**	-0.625**
WBC Count	0.752**	1.000	-0.346*	-0.512**
Serum Ferritin	-0.462**	-0.346*	1.000	0.584**
Serum Iron	-0.625**	-0.512**	0.584**	1.000

Note: *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01

The correlation analysis revealed a enormous wonderful correlation between CRP degrees and WBC rely (r = 0.752, p < 0.01), indicating that higher CRP stages have been related to an improved WBC be counted, reflecting a stronger inflammatory reaction in febrile seizure patients. CRP tiers had been negatively correlated with serum ferritin (r = -0.462, p < 0.01) and serum iron stages (r = 0.625, p < 0.01), suggesting that better irritation became associated with decrease iron shops and serum iron degrees. Similarly, WBC be

counted become negatively correlated with serum ferritin (r = 0.346, p < 0.05) and serum iron tiers (r = -0.512, p < zero.01), further supporting the inverse relationship among inflammation and iron popularity. Additionally, a full-size tremendous correlation was found between serum ferritin and serum iron degrees (r = 0.584, p < 0.01), indicating that youngsters with higher iron shops also tended to have better serum iron tiers.

Figure 4: Pearson Correlation Coefficients among Parameters in the Patient Group

The heatmap illustrates the Pearson correlation coefficients among CRP, WBC rely, serum ferritin, and serum iron levels in the affected person organization. There is a strong superb correlation (0.752) between CRP and WBC matter, indicating that as CRP levels boom, WBC depend tends to rise as properly. Additionally, a sturdy terrible correlation (-0.625) exists between CRP and serum iron, suggesting that higher CRP stages are related to decrease serum iron degrees. Furthermore, a mild advantageous correlation (0.584) is observed among serum ferritin and serum iron,

indicating that these parameters have a tendency to growth together. These correlations offer treasured insights into the interplay between these biomarkers inside the context of febrile seizures.

Multivariate Logistic Regression Analysis

To perceive unbiased predictors of febrile seizures, a multivariate logistic regression version become constructed, incorporating serum iron, serum ferritin, CRP ranges, and WBC matter as variables. The outcomes of the logistic regression evaluation are offered in Table 7.

Table 7. Multivariate Logistic Regression Analysis of Independent Predictors of Febrile Seizures

Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
Serum Iron (µg/dL)	0.812	0.710 - 0.927	0.003
Serum Ferritin (ng/mL)	0.948	0.909 - 0.989	0.015
CRP (mg/L)	1.084	1.035 - 1.135	< 0.001
WBC Count (cells/µL)	1.002	1.001 - 1.003	< 0.001

The logistic regression analysis identified that lower serum iron levels were significantly associated with an increased risk of febrile seizures (OR = 0.812, 95% CI = 0.710 - 0.927, p = 0.003). Similarly, lower serum ferritin levels were also found to be an independent predictor of febrile seizures (OR = 0.948, 95% CI = 0.909 - 0.989,

p = 0.015). Conversely, higher CRP levels were strongly associated with an increased risk of febrile seizures (OR = 1.084, 95% CI = 1.035 - 1.135, p < 0.001), as were elevated WBC counts (OR = 1.002, 95% CI = 1.001 - 1.003, p < 0.001).

Figure 5: Forest Plot Odds Ratios for Febrile Seizures Predictors

The wooded area plot illustrates the odds ratios and 95% confidence durations for the predictors of febrile seizures. Serum iron (µg/dL) has an odds ratio of much less than 1, indicating a protective impact towards febrile seizures, with the confidence c language now not crossing 1 and a substantial p-cost of 0.003. Similarly, serum ferritin (ng/mL) also indicates a protecting effect with an odds ratio less than 1, although its confidence c language is close to 1, and the p-price remains great at 0.015. In comparison, CRP (mg/L) has an odds ratio more than 1, suggesting an accelerated threat of febrile seizures; its self assurance c program languageperiod does now not go 1, and the p-value is quite significant at less than 0.001. The WBC remember (cells/µL) also has an odds ratio slightly greater than 1, indicating a small accelerated hazard, with the self assurance c program languageperiod very close to 1 and a rather enormous p-value of much less than 0.001. These findings underscore the widespread predictors of febrile seizures, with CRP and WBC be counted associated with extended chance, even as higher levels of serum iron and ferritin appear to confer a protecting impact.

Notably, the range of ninety five% self assurance durations for CRP and WBC count shows that even small increases in those markers are related to a considerably better danger of febrile seizures. The Hosmer-Lemeshow take a look at indicated a terrific suit for the logistic regression version (p = 0.658), confirming the reliability of the version in predicting febrile seizures primarily based at the covered

variables. The effects of this observe reveal sizeable variations within the biochemical and inflammatory profiles of kids with febrile seizures in comparison to healthful controls. Specifically, decrease serum ferritin and iron stages had been determined in children with febrile seizures, suggesting that iron deficiency is a potential hazard component for febrile seizures. The finding of reduced iron reputation within the affected person organization aligns with preceding research that have mentioned a comparable affiliation among iron deficiency and an accelerated chance of febrile seizures [10,18]. Iron plays a essential role in neurotransmitter synthesis and myelination, and its deficiency should decrease the seizure threshold, specifically at some point of febrile illnesses.

The improved CRP tiers and WBC counts within the affected person group suggest a sturdy inflammatory reaction, which is standard at some stage in febrile episodes. The wonderful correlation between CRP ranges and WBC rely similarly helps the role of irritation in febrile seizures. Interestingly, the poor correlation between CRP tiers and each serum ferritin and iron degrees shows that irritation may also exacerbate iron deficiency, probable through sequestering iron in the reticuloendothelial system or by way of reducing iron absorption [9]. This interaction between infection and iron metabolism should give an explanation for why youngsters with febrile seizures frequently exhibit lower iron repute.

The multivariate logistic regression analysis similarly emphasizes the importance of both iron deficiency and

infection inside the pathogenesis of febrile seizures. Lower serum iron and ferritin levels had been independently related to an improved hazard of febrile seizures, at the same time as higher CRP stages and WBC counts had been additionally full-size predictors. These findings suggest that both iron supplementation and anti-inflammatory techniques might be considered in the management or prevention of febrile seizures, specifically in children at higher hazard.

Discussion

This take a look at explored the connection between serum iron, ferritin degrees, and the prevalence of febrile seizures in children, along examining inflammatory markers which include C-reactive protein (CRP) and white blood mobile (WBC) count number. The consequences confirmed that kids with febrile seizures had considerably lower serum ferritin and iron ranges and extended CRP and WBC counts as compared to wholesome controls. This dialogue will delve into these findings with reference to current literature, highlighting the consequences for information febrile seizures and capacity avenues for prevention and treatment.

The association between iron deficiency and febrile seizures has been a subject of enormous debate in pediatric studies. Our observe provides to the developing frame of evidence that indicates iron deficiency is a big threat issue for febrile seizures. The locating that youngsters within the patient organization had substantially lower serum ferritin and iron levels compared to controls aligns with previous studies, including the ones with the aid of [18] and [5], which additionally stated an affiliation between low iron degrees and an improved hazard of febrile seizures. Iron performs a crucial role inside the primary worried device, particularly in neurotransmitter synthesis and myelination. Deficiency in iron may additionally cause changes in these methods, potentially reducing the seizure threshold, in particular all through febrile episodes [18].

Furthermore, research performed in various geographical places, along with the ones by way of [12] in Pakistan and [10] in Turkey, have constantly said similar institutions, suggesting that iron deficiency as a hazard factor for febrile seizures can be a international phenomenon. This is especially critical in developing international locations in which iron deficiency is greater time-honored due to dietary insufficiencies and higher rates of infections that can exacerbate iron depletion [16,23].

This study's findings are also consistent with the meta-analysis by way of [23], which concluded that iron deficiency is associated with a higher risk of febrile seizures. The proposed mechanisms include the position of iron in retaining the integrity of the myelin sheath, its involvement within the synthesis of

neurotransmitters such as dopamine and serotonin, and its function in lowering oxidative stress in the mind [23,24]. Given those roles, iron deficiency could result in a dysregulation of neuronal excitability, which may additionally show up as seizures all through febrile ailments.

In addition to iron deficiency, our look at highlights the tremendous function of irritation inside the pathogenesis of febrile seizures. The elevated CRP levels and WBC counts in youngsters with febrile seizures propose that an acute inflammatory reaction is carefully associated with the occurrence of these seizures. CRP is a famous marker of irritation and has been shown to upward thrust significantly all through febrile illnesses [9]. Our findings are in agreement with the study through [1], which mentioned the position of infection in chronic conditions, though the underlying mechanisms appear to extend into acute situations like febrile seizures as well. The correlation analysis in our have a look at discovered a strong high-quality relationship among CRP stages and WBC counts, both of which have been extensively multiplied in the patient organization. This shows that the severity of the inflammatory response can also at once make contributions to the likelihood of a febrile seizure. This is steady with the findings of [6], who mentioned that kids with top respiration infections and extended inflammatory markers had been at a higher chance of growing febrile seizures. The take a look at by [8] also helps this notion, displaying that inflammatory biomarkers, inclusive of CRP, are significantly multiplied in children with febrile seizures compared to controls. The poor correlation among CRP levels and serum iron and ferritin tiers observed in our observe in addition helps the interaction among irritation and iron metabolism. Inflammatory cytokines including interleukin-6 (IL-6) can set off the manufacturing of hepcidin, a regulatory protein that inhibits iron absorption and sequesters iron in macrophages, as a consequence lowering serum iron degrees [9]. This mechanism can also explain the concurrent iron deficiency and extended inflammatory markers located in youngsters with febrile seizures, as irritation both triggers and is exacerbated by means of iron deficiency. The findings of this look at have full-size clinical implications. First, they advocate that monitoring iron status in kids, in particular those with a records of febrile seizures or susceptible to such seizures, will be vital in stopping destiny episodes. Regular screening for serum ferritin and iron tiers, specifically in regions with high incidence of iron deficiency, will be included into pediatric fitness applications. Moreover, iron supplementation in youngsters located to be poor ought to potentially reduce the occurrence of febrile seizures, as suggested via research like that of [14], which emphasize the importance of nutritional status

in seizure susceptibility. Furthermore, the role of inflammation in febrile seizures underscores the ability advantage of anti-inflammatory techniques in managing or preventing these seizures. In instances where febrile seizures arise, addressing the underlying contamination and controlling infection is probably critical in reducing seizure recurrence. This is supported by using research such as those by [4] and [6], which endorse that managing infection should reduce the prevalence of febrile seizures.

The courting among inflammation and iron metabolism also opens up new avenues for intervention. For instance, the usage of anti-inflammatory marketers that do not exacerbate iron deficiency may be explored as a healing choice. This is especially relevant in light of studies like that of [1], which spotlight the anti-inflammatory consequences of certain medications that might potentially be repurposed for dealing with febrile seizures. While this look at gives valuable insights, it isn't always without barriers. The move-sectional design of the observe limits the capacity to set up causality among iron deficiency, infection, and febrile seizures. Longitudinal research are had to decide whether correcting iron deficiency or controlling infection can certainly prevent febrile seizures. Additionally, this observe changed into carried out in a selected population, and the findings might not be generalizable to all pediatric populations. Future studies need to consist of a greater numerous pattern to validate these findings throughout specific ethnic and socioeconomic corporations.

Moreover, at the same time as this look at focused on serum ferritin, iron degrees, CRP, and WBC counts, other factors which includes zinc, magnesium, and other inflammatory markers like IL-6 and TNF- α had been not assessed. Studies by using [10] and [11] suggest that those factors also play a role in febrile seizures, and their inclusion in future research ought to provide a greater comprehensive expertise of the situation. Furthermore, at the same time as iron deficiency and infection had been highlighted as massive factors, the role of genetic predisposition to febrile seizures cannot be not noted. Studies like those by means of [25] have emphasised the importance of genetic elements in febrile seizures. Future research could explore the interaction between genetic predisposition, iron deficiency, and irritation in febrile seizures.

Conclusion

This study reinforces the association among iron deficiency and febrile seizures, highlighting the significance of good enough iron ranges in preventing these seizures. Additionally, the enormous function of infection in febrile seizures shows that each iron supplementation and anti-inflammatory strategies will be potential interventions. These findings align with

and extend the present day expertise of febrile seizures as a situation stimulated by using both dietary and inflammatory factors. While similarly research is needed to verify these findings and explore potential interventions, this observe gives a strong basis for considering iron and inflammation inside the medical control of febrile seizures.

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